

Smarandache isotopy theory of Smarandache: quasigroups and loops

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Abstract The concept of Smarandache isotopy is introduced and its study is explored for Smarandache: groupoids, quasigroups and loops just like the study of isotopy theory was carried out for groupoids, quasigroups and loops. The exploration includes: Smarandache; isotopy and isomorphy classes, Smarandache f, g principal isotopes and G-Smarandache loops.

Keywords Smarandache, groupoids, quasigroups, loops, f, g principal isotopes.

§1. Introduction

In 2002, W. B. Vasantha Kandasamy initiated the study of Smarandache loops in her book [12] where she introduced over 75 Smarandache concepts in loops. In her paper [13], she defined a Smarandache loop (S-loop) as a loop with at least a subloop which forms a subgroup under the binary operation of the loop. For more on loops and their properties, readers should check [11], [1], [3], [4], [5] and [12]. In [12], Page 102, the author introduced Smarandache isotopes of loops particularly Smarandache principal isotopes. She has also introduced the Smarandache concept in some other algebraic structures as [14][15][16][17][18][19] account. The present author has contributed to the study of S-quasigroups and S-loops in [6], [7] and [8] while Muktibodh [10] did a study on the first.

In this study, the concept of Smarandache isotopy will be introduced and its study will be explored in Smarandache: groupoids, quasigroups and loops just like the study of isotopy theory was carried out for groupoids, quasigroups and loops as summarized in Bruck [1], Dene and Keedwell [4], Pflugfelder [11].

§2. Definitions and notations

Definition 2.1. Let L be a non-empty set. Define a binary operation (\cdot) on L : If $x \cdot y \in L \forall x, y \in L$, (L, \cdot) is called a groupoid. If the system of equations $a \cdot x = b$ and $y \cdot a = b$ have unique solutions for x and y respectively, then (L, \cdot) is called a quasigroup. Furthermore, if there exists a unique element $e \in L$ called the identity element such that $\forall x \in L, x \cdot e = e \cdot x = x$, (L, \cdot) is called a loop.

If there exists at least a non-empty and non-trivial subset M of a groupoid (quasigroup or semigroup or loop) L such that (M, \cdot) is a non-trivial subsemigroup (subgroup or subgroup

or subgroup) of (L, \cdot) , then L is called a Smarandache: groupoid(S-groupoid)(quasigroup(S-quasigroup) or semigroup(S-semigroup) or loop(S-loop)) with Smarandache: subsemigroup(S-subsemigroup)(subgroup(S-subgroup) or subgroup(S-subgroup) or subgroup(S-subgroup)) M .

Let (G, \cdot) be a quasigroup(loop). The bijection $L_x : G \rightarrow G$ defined as $yL_x = x \cdot y \forall x, y \in G$ is called a left translation(multiplication) of G while the bijection $R_x : G \rightarrow G$ defined as $yR_x = y \cdot x \forall x, y \in G$ is called a right translation(multiplication) of G .

The set $SYM(L, \cdot) = SYM(L)$ of all bijections in a groupoid (L, \cdot) forms a group called the permutation(symmetric) group of the groupoid (L, \cdot) .

Definition 2.2. If (L, \cdot) and (G, \circ) are two distinct groupoids, then the triple $(U, V, W) : (L, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$ such that $U, V, W : L \rightarrow G$ are bijections is called an isotopism if and only if

$$xU \circ yV = (x \cdot y)W \forall x, y \in L.$$

So we call L and G groupoid isotopes. If $L = G$ and $W = I$ (identity mapping) then (U, V, I) is called a principal isotopism, so we call G a principal isotope of L . But if in addition G is a quasigroup such that for some $f, g \in G, U = R_g$ and $V = L_f$, then $(R_g, L_f, I) : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$ is called an f, g -principal isotopism while (G, \cdot) and (G, \circ) are called quasigroup isotopes.

If $U = V = W$, then U is called an isomorphism, hence we write $(L, \cdot) \cong (G, \circ)$. A loop (L, \cdot) is called a G-loop if and only if $(L, \cdot) \cong (G, \circ)$ for all loop isotopes (G, \circ) of (L, \cdot) .

Now, if (L, \cdot) and (G, \circ) are S-groupoids with S-subsemigroups L' and G' respectively such that $(G')A = L'$, where $A \in \{U, V, W\}$, then the isotopism $(U, V, W) : (L, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$ is called a Smarandache isotopism(S-isotopism). Consequently, if $W = I$ the triple (U, V, I) is called a Smarandache principal isotopism. But if in addition G is a S-quasigroup with S-subgroup H' such that for some $f, g \in H, U = R_g$ and $V = L_f$, and $(R_g, L_f, I) : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$ is an isotopism, then the triple is called a Smarandache f, g -principal isotopism while f and g are called Smarandache elements(S-elements).

Thus, if $U = V = W$, then U is called a Smarandache isomorphism, hence we write $(L, \cdot) \simeq (G, \circ)$. An S-loop (L, \cdot) is called a G-Smarandache loop(GS-loop) if and only if $(L, \cdot) \simeq (G, \circ)$ for all loop isotopes(or particularly all S-loop isotopes) (G, \circ) of (L, \cdot) .

Example 2.1. The systems (L, \cdot) and $(L, *)$, $L = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with the multiplication tables below are S-quasigroups with S-subgroups (L', \cdot) and $(L'', *)$ respectively, $L' = \{0, 1\}$ and $L'' = \{1, 2\}$. (L, \cdot) is taken from Example 2.2 of [10]. The triple (U, V, W) such that

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 4 & 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } W = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 0 & 4 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

are permutations on L , is an S-isotopism of (L, \cdot) onto $(L, *)$. Notice that $A(L') = L''$ for all $A \in \{U, V, W\}$ and $U, V, W : L' \rightarrow L''$ are all bijections.

·	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	3	4	2
1	1	0	2	3	4
2	3	4	1	2	0
3	4	2	0	1	3
4	2	3	4	0	1

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	1	0	4	2	3
1	3	1	2	0	4
2	4	2	1	3	0
3	0	4	3	1	2
4	2	3	0	4	1

Example 2.2. According to Example 4.2.2 of [15], the system (\mathbb{Z}_6, \times_6) i.e the set $L = \mathbb{Z}_6$ under multiplication modulo 6 is an S-semigroup with S-subgroups (L', \times_6) and (L'', \times_6) , $L' = \{2, 4\}$ and $L'' = \{1, 5\}$. This can be deduced from its multiplication table, below. The triple (U, V, W) such that

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 4 & 3 & 5 & 1 & 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, V = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 & 4 & 5 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } W = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \\ 1 & 0 & 5 & 4 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

are permutations on L , is an S-isotopism of (\mathbb{Z}_6, \times_6) unto an S-semigroup $(\mathbb{Z}_6, *)$ with S-subgroups $(L''', *)$ and $(L'''' , *)$, $L''' = \{2, 5\}$ and $L'''' = \{0, 3\}$ as shown in the second table below. Notice that $A(L') = L'''$ and $A(L'') = L''''$ for all $A \in \{U, V, W\}$ and $U, V, W : L' \rightarrow L'''$ and $U, V, W : L'' \rightarrow L''''$ are all bijections.

\times_6	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	2	3	4	5
2	0	2	4	0	2	4
3	0	3	0	3	0	3
4	0	4	2	0	4	2
5	0	5	4	3	2	1

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	1	2	3	4	5
1	4	1	1	4	4	1
2	5	1	5	2	1	2
3	3	1	5	0	4	2
4	1	1	1	1	1	1
5	2	1	2	5	1	5

Remark 2.1. Taking careful look at Definition 2.2 and comparing it with Definition 4.4.1[12], it will be observed that the author did not allow the component bijections U, V and W in (U, V, W) to act on the whole S-loop L but only on the S-subloop(S-subgroup) L' . We feel this is necessary to adjust here so that the set $L - L'$ is not out of the study. Apart from this, our adjustment here will allow the study of Smarandache isotopy to be explorable. Therefore, the S-isotopism and S-isomorphism here are clearly special types of relations(isotopism and isomorphism) on the whole domain into the whole co-domain but those of Vasantha Kandasamy [12] only take care of the structure of the elements in the S-subloop and not the S-loop. Nevertheless, we do not fault her study for we think she defined them to apply them to some life problems as an applied algebraist.

§3. Smarandache Isotopy and Isomorphism classes

Theorem 3.1. Let $\mathfrak{G} = \{(G_\omega, \circ_\omega)\}_{\omega \in \Omega}$ be a set of distinct S-groupoids with a corresponding set of S-subsemigroups $\mathfrak{H} = \{(H_\omega, \circ_\omega)\}_{\omega \in \Omega}$. Define a relation \sim on \mathfrak{G} such that for all $(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}), (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \in \mathfrak{G}$, where $\omega_i, \omega_j \in \Omega$,

$$(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \sim (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \iff (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \text{ and } (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \text{ are S-isotopic.}$$

Then \sim is an equivalence relation on \mathfrak{G} .

Proof. Let $(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}), (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}), (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k}) \in \mathfrak{G}$, where $\omega_i, \omega_j, \omega_k \in \Omega$.

Reflexivity If $I : G_{\omega_i} \rightarrow G_{\omega_i}$ is the identity mapping, then

$$xI \circ_{\omega_i} yI = (x \circ_{\omega_i} y)I \quad \forall x, y \in G_{\omega_i} \implies \text{the triple } (I, I, I) : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \rightarrow (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i})$$

is an S-isotopism since $(H_{\omega_i})I = H_{\omega_i} \quad \forall \omega_i \in \Omega$. In fact, it can be simply deduced that every S-groupoid is S-isomorphic to itself.

Symmetry Let $(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \sim (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j})$. Then there exist bijections

$$U, V, W : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \text{ such that } (H_{\omega_i})A = H_{\omega_j} \quad \forall A \in \{U, V, W\}$$

so that the triple

$$\alpha = (U, V, W) : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j})$$

is an isotopism. Since each of U, V, W is bijective, then their inverses

$$U^{-1}, V^{-1}, W^{-1} : (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i})$$

are bijective. In fact, $(H_{\omega_j})A^{-1} = H_{\omega_i} \quad \forall A \in \{U, V, W\}$ since A is bijective so that the triple

$$\alpha^{-1} = (U^{-1}, V^{-1}, W^{-1}) : (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i})$$

is an isotopism. Thus, $(G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \sim (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i})$.

Transitivity Let $(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \sim (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j})$ and $(G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \sim (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$. Then there exist bijections

$$U_1, V_1, W_1 : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \text{ and } U_2, V_2, W_2 : (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$$

$$\text{such that } (H_{\omega_i})A = H_{\omega_j} \quad \forall A \in \{U_1, V_1, W_1\}$$

and $(H_{\omega_j})B = H_{\omega_k} \quad \forall B \in \{U_2, V_2, W_2\}$ so that the triples

$$\alpha_1 = (U_1, V_1, W_1) : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \text{ and}$$

$$\alpha_2 = (U_2, V_2, W_2) : (G_{\omega_j}, \circ_{\omega_j}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$$

are isotopisms. Since each of $U_i, V_i, W_i, i = 1, 2$, is bijective, then

$$U_3 = U_1U_2, V_3 = V_1V_2, W_3 = W_1W_2 : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$$

are bijections such that $(H_{\omega_i})A_3 = (H_{\omega_i})A_1A_2 = (H_{\omega_j})A_2 = H_{\omega_k}$ so that the triple

$$\alpha_3 = \alpha_1\alpha_2 = (U_3, V_3, W_3) : (G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \longrightarrow (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$$

is an isotopism. Thus, $(G_{\omega_i}, \circ_{\omega_i}) \sim (G_{\omega_k}, \circ_{\omega_k})$.

Remark 3.1. As a follow up to Theorem 3.1, the elements of the set \mathfrak{G}/\sim will be referred to as Smarandache isotopy classes(S-isotopy classes). Similarly, if \sim meant "S-isomorphism" in Theorem 3.1, then the elements of \mathfrak{G}/\sim will be referred to as Smarandache isomorphism classes(S-isomorphism classes). Just like isotopy has an advantage over isomorphism in the classification of loops, so also S-isotopy will have advantage over S-isomorphism in the classification of S-loops.

Corollary 3.1. Let $\mathcal{L}_n, \mathcal{SL}_n$ and \mathcal{NSL}_n be the sets of; all finite loops of order n ; all finite S-loops of order n and all finite non S-loops of order n respectively.

1. If \mathcal{A}_i^n and \mathcal{B}_i^n represent the isomorphism class of \mathcal{L}_n and the S-isomorphism class of \mathcal{SL}_n respectively, then

- (a) $|\mathcal{SL}_n| + |\mathcal{NSL}_n| = |\mathcal{L}_n|;$
- (i) $|\mathcal{SL}_5| + |\mathcal{NSL}_5| = 56,$
- (ii) $|\mathcal{SL}_6| + |\mathcal{NSL}_6| = 9,408$
- (iii) $|\mathcal{SL}_7| + |\mathcal{NSL}_7| = 16,942,080.$
- (b) $|\mathcal{NSL}_n| = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mathcal{A}_i^n| - \sum_{i=1}^n |\mathcal{B}_i^n|;$
- (i) $|\mathcal{NSL}_5| = \sum_{i=1}^6 |\mathcal{A}_i^5| - \sum_{i=1}^6 |\mathcal{B}_i^5|,$
- (ii) $|\mathcal{NSL}_6| = \sum_{i=1}^{109} |\mathcal{A}_i^6| - \sum_{i=1}^{109} |\mathcal{B}_i^6|$
- (iii) $|\mathcal{NSL}_7| = \sum_{i=1}^{23,746} |\mathcal{A}_i^7| - \sum_{i=1}^{23,746} |\mathcal{B}_i^7|.$

2. If \mathfrak{A}_i^n and \mathfrak{B}_i^n represent the isotopy class of \mathcal{L}_n and the S-isotopy class of \mathcal{SL}_n respectively, then

$$|\mathcal{NSL}_n| = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mathfrak{A}_i^n| - \sum_{i=1}^n |\mathfrak{B}_i^n|;$$

- (i) $|\mathcal{NSL}_5| = \sum_{i=1}^2 |\mathfrak{A}_i^5| - \sum_{i=1}^2 |\mathfrak{B}_i^5|,$
- (ii) $|\mathcal{NSL}_6| = \sum_{i=1}^{22} |\mathfrak{A}_i^6| - \sum_{i=1}^{22} |\mathfrak{B}_i^6|$ and
- (iii) $|\mathcal{NSL}_7| = \sum_{i=1}^{564} |\mathfrak{A}_i^7| - \sum_{i=1}^{564} |\mathfrak{B}_i^7|.$

Proof. An S-loop is an S-groupoid. Thus by Theorem 3.1, we have S-isomorphism classes and S-isotopy classes. Recall that $|\mathcal{L}_n| = |\mathcal{SL}_n| + |\mathcal{NSL}_n| - |\mathcal{SL}_n \cap \mathcal{NSL}_n|$ but $\mathcal{SL}_n \cap \mathcal{NSL}_n = \emptyset$ so $|\mathcal{L}_n| = |\mathcal{SL}_n| + |\mathcal{NSL}_n|$. As stated and shown in [11], [15], [2] and [9], the facts in Table 1 are true where n is the order of a finite loop. Hence the claims follow.

Question 3.1. How many S-loops are in the family \mathcal{L}_n ? That is, what is $|\mathcal{SL}_n|$ or $|\mathcal{NSL}_n|$.

Theorem 3.2. Let (G, \cdot) be a finite S-groupoid of order n with a finite S-subsemigroup (H, \cdot) of order m . Also, let

$$ISOT(G, \cdot), SISISOT(G, \cdot) \text{ and } \mathcal{N}SISISOT(G, \cdot)$$

be the sets of all isotopisms, S-isotopisms and non S-isotopisms of (G, \cdot) . Then,

$$ISOT(G, \cdot) \text{ is a group and } SISISOT(G, \cdot) \leq ISOT(G, \cdot).$$

Furthermore:

1. $|ISOT(G, \cdot)| = (n!)^3$;
2. $|SISISOT(G, \cdot)| = (m!)^3$;
3. $|\mathcal{N}SISISOT(G, \cdot)| = (n!)^3 - (m!)^3$.

Proof.

1. This has been shown to be true in [Theorem 4.1.1, [4]].
2. An S-isotopism is an isotopism. So, $SISISOT(G, \cdot) \subset ISOT(G, \cdot)$. Thus, we need to just verify the axioms of a group to show that $SISISOT(G, \cdot) \leq ISOT(G, \cdot)$. These can be done using the proofs of reflexivity, symmetry and transitivity in Theorem 3.1 as guides. For all triples

$$\alpha \in SISISOT(G, \cdot) \text{ such that } \alpha = (U, V, W) : (G, \cdot) \longrightarrow (G, \circ),$$

where (G, \cdot) and (G, \circ) are S-groupoids with S-subgroups (H, \cdot) and (K, \circ) respectively, we can set

$$U' := U|_H, V' := V|_H \text{ and } W' := W|_H \text{ since } A(H) = K \ \forall A \in \{U, V, W\},$$

so that $SISISOT(H, \cdot) = \{(U', V', W')\}$. This is possible because of the following arguments.

Let

$$X = \left\{ f' := f|_H \mid f : G \longrightarrow G, f : H \longrightarrow K \text{ is bijective and } f(H) = K \right\}.$$

Let

$$SYM(H, K) = \{\text{bijections from } H \text{ unto } K\}.$$

n	5	6	7
$ \mathcal{L}_n $	56	9, 408	16, 942, 080
$\{\mathcal{A}_i^n\}_{i=1}^k$	$k = 6$	$k = 109$	$k = 23, 746$
$\{\mathcal{Q}_i^n\}_{i=1}^m$	$m = 2$	$m = 22$	$m = 564$

Table 1: Enumeration of Isomorphy and Isotopy classes of finite loops of small order

By definition, it is easy to see that $X \subseteq SYM(H, K)$. Now, for all $U \in SYM(H, K)$, define $U : H^c \rightarrow K^c$ so that $U : G \rightarrow G$ is a bijection since $|H| = |K|$ implies $|H^c| = |K^c|$. Thus, $SYM(H, K) \subseteq X$ so that $SYM(H, K) = X$.

Given that $|H| = m$, then it follows from (1) that

$$|ISOT(H, \cdot)| = (m!)^3 \text{ so that } |SISOT(G, \cdot)| = (m!)^3 \text{ since } SYM(H, K) = X.$$

3.

$$\mathcal{N}SISOT(G, \cdot) = (SISOT(G, \cdot))^c.$$

So, the identity isotopism

$$(I, I, I) \notin \mathcal{N}SISOT(G, \cdot), \text{ hence } \mathcal{N}SISOT(G, \cdot) \not\subseteq ISOT(G, \cdot).$$

Furthermore,

$$|\mathcal{N}SISOT(G, \cdot)| = (n!)^3 - (m!)^3.$$

Corollary 3.2. Let (G, \cdot) be a finite S-groupoid of order n with an S-subsemigroup (H, \cdot) . If $ISOT(G, \cdot)$ is the group of all isotopisms of (G, \cdot) and S_n is the symmetric group of degree n , then

$$ISOT(G, \cdot) \simeq S_n \times S_n \times S_n.$$

Proof. As concluded in [Corollary 1, [4]], $ISOT(G, \cdot) \cong S_n \times S_n \times S_n$. Let $\mathcal{P}ISOT(G, \cdot)$ be the set of all principal isotopisms on (G, \cdot) . $\mathcal{P}ISOT(G, \cdot)$ is an S-subgroup in $ISOT(G, \cdot)$ while $S_n \times S_n \times \{I\}$ is an S-subgroup in $S_n \times S_n \times S_n$. If

$$\Upsilon : ISOT(G, \cdot) \rightarrow S_n \times S_n \times S_n \text{ is defined as}$$

$$\Upsilon((A, B, I)) = \langle A, B, I \rangle \quad \forall (A, B, I) \in ISOT(G, \cdot),$$

then

$$\Upsilon(\mathcal{P}ISOT(G, \cdot)) = S_n \times S_n \times \{I\}. \quad \therefore ISOT(G, \cdot) \simeq S_n \times S_n \times S_n.$$

§4. Smarandache f, g -Isotopes of Smarandache loops

Theorem 4.1. Let (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ be S-groupoids. If (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ are S-isotopic, then $(H, *)$ is S-isomorphic to some Smarandache principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) .

Proof. Since (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ are S-isotopic S-groupoids with S-subsemigroups (G_1, \cdot) and $(H_1, *)$, then there exist bijections $U, V, W : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (H, *)$ such that the triple $\alpha = (U, V, W) : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (H, *)$ is an isotopism and $(G_1)A = H_1 \quad \forall A \in \{U, V, W\}$. To prove the claim of this theorem, it suffices to produce a closed binary operation $'*'$ on G , bijections $X, Y : G \rightarrow G$, and bijection $Z : G \rightarrow H$ so that

- the triple $\beta = (X, Y, I) : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$ is a Smarandache principal isotopism and
- $Z : (G, \circ) \rightarrow (H, *)$ is an S-isomorphism or the triple $\gamma = (Z, Z, Z) : (G, \circ) \rightarrow (H, *)$ is an S-isotopism.

Thus, we need (G, \circ) so that the commutative diagram below is true:

because following the proof of transitivity in Theorem 3.1, $\alpha = \beta\gamma$ which implies $(U, V, W) = (XZ, YZ, Z)$ and so we can make the choices; $Z = W$, $Y = VW^{-1}$, and $X = UW^{-1}$ and consequently,

$$x \cdot y = xUW^{-1} \circ VW^{-1} \iff x \circ y = xWU^{-1} \cdot yWV^{-1} \forall x, y \in G.$$

Hence, (G, \circ) is a groupoid principal isotope of (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ is an isomorph of (G, \circ) . It remains to show that these two relationships are Smarandache.

Note that $((H_1)Z^{-1}, \circ) = (G_1, \circ)$ is a non-trivial subsemigroup in (G, \circ) . Thus, (G, \circ) is an S-groupoid. So $(G, \circ) \simeq (H, *)$. (G, \cdot) and (G, \circ) are Smarandache principal isotopes because $(G_1)UW^{-1} = (H_1)W^{-1} = (H_1)Z^{-1} = G_1$ and $(G_1)VW^{-1} = (H_1)W^{-1} = (H_1)Z^{-1} = G_1$.

Corollary 4.1. Let (G, \cdot) be an S-groupoid with an arbitrary groupoid isotope $(H, *)$. Any such groupoid $(H, *)$ is an S-groupoid if and only if all the principal isotopes of (G, \cdot) are S-groupoids.

Proof. By classical result in principal isotopy [[11], III.1.4 Theorem], if (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ are isotopic groupoids, then $(H, *)$ is isomorphic to some principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) . Assuming $(H, *)$ is an S-groupoid then since $(H, *) \cong (G, \circ)$, (G, \circ) is an S-groupoid. Conversely, let us assume all the principal isotopes of (G, \cdot) are S-groupoids. Since $(H, *) \cong (G, \circ)$, then $(H, *)$ is an S-groupoid.

Theorem 4.2. Let (G, \cdot) be an S-quasigroup. If $(H, *)$ is an S-loop which is S-isotopic to (G, \cdot) , then there exist S-elements f and g so that $(H, *)$ is S-isomorphic to a Smarandache f, g principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) .

Proof. An S-quasigroup and an S-loop are S-groupoids. So by Theorem 4.1, $(H, *)$ is S-isomorphic to a Smarandache principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) . Let $\alpha = (U, V, I)$ be the Smarandache principal isotopism of (G, \cdot) onto (G, \circ) . Since $(H, *)$ is a S-loop and $(G, \circ) \simeq (H, *)$ implies that $(G, \circ) \cong (H, *)$, then (G, \circ) is necessarily an S-loop and consequently, (G, \circ) has a two-sided identity element say e and an S-subgroup (G_2, \circ) . Let $\alpha = (U, V, I)$ be the Smarandache principal isotopism of (G, \cdot) onto (G, \circ) . Then,

$$xU \circ yV = x \cdot y \forall x, y \in G \iff x \circ y = xU^{-1} \cdot yV^{-1} \forall x, y \in G.$$

So,

$$y = e \circ y = eU^{-1} \cdot yV^{-1} = yV^{-1}L_{eU^{-1}} \forall y \in G \text{ and } x = x \circ e = xU^{-1} \cdot eV^{-1} = xU^{-1}R_{eV^{-1}} \forall x \in G.$$

Assign $f = eU^{-1}, g = eV^{-1} \in G_2$. This assignments are well defined and hence $V = L_f$ and $U = R_g$. So that $\alpha = (R_g, L_f, I)$ is a Smarandache f, g principal isotopism of (G, \circ) onto (G, \cdot) . This completes the proof.

Corollary 4.2. Let (G, \cdot) be an S-quasigroup(S-loop) with an arbitrary groupoid isotope $(H, *)$. Any such groupoid $(H, *)$ is an S-quasigroup(S-loop) if and only if all the principal isotopes of (G, \cdot) are S-quasigroups(S-loops).

Proof. This follows immediately from Corollary 4.1, since an S-quasigroup and an S-loop are S-groupoids.

Corollary 4.3. If (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ are S-loops which are S-isotopic, then there exist S-elements f and g so that $(H, *)$ is S-isomorphic to a Smarandache f, g principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) .

Proof. An S-loop is an S-quasigroup. So the claim follows from Theorem 4.2.

§5. G-Smarandache loops

Lemma 5.1. Let (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ be S-isotopic S-loops. If (G, \cdot) is a group, then (G, \cdot) and $(H, *)$ are S-isomorphic groups.

Proof. By Corollary 4.3, there exist S-elements f and g in (G, \cdot) so that $(H, *) \simeq (G, \circ)$ such that (G, \circ) is a Smarandache f, g principal isotope of (G, \cdot) .

Let us set the mapping $\psi := R_{f \cdot g} = R_{fg} : G \rightarrow G$. This mapping is bijective. Now, let us consider when $\psi := R_{fg} : (G, \cdot) \rightarrow (G, \circ)$. Since (G, \cdot) is associative and $x \circ y = xR_g^{-1} \cdot yL_f^{-1} \forall x, y \in G$, the following arguments are true.

$x\psi \circ y\psi = x\psi R_g^{-1} \cdot y\psi L_f^{-1} = xR_{fg}R_g^{-1} \cdot yR_{fg}L_f^{-1} = x \cdot fg \cdot g^{-1} \cdot f^{-1} \cdot y \cdot fg = x \cdot y \cdot fg = (x \cdot y)R_{fg} = (x \cdot y)\psi \forall x, y \in G$. So, $(G, \cdot) \cong (G, \circ)$. Thus, (G, \circ) is a group. If (G_1, \cdot) and (G_1, \circ) are the S-subgroups in (G, \cdot) and (G, \circ) , then $((G_1, \cdot))R_{fg} = (G_1, \circ)$. Hence, $(G, \cdot) \simeq (G, \circ)$.

$\therefore (G, \cdot) \simeq (H, *)$ and $(H, *)$ is a group.

Corollary 5.1. Every group which is an S-loop is a GS-loop.

Proof. This follows immediately from Lemma 5.1 and the fact that a group is a G-loop.

Corollary 5.2. An S-loop is S-isomorphic to all its S-loop S-isotopes if and only if it is S-isomorphic to all its Smarandache f, g principal isotopes.

Proof. Let (G, \cdot) be an S-loop with arbitrary S-isotope $(H, *)$. Let us assume that $(G, \cdot) \simeq (H, *)$. From Corollary 4.3, for any arbitrary S-isotope $(H, *)$ of (G, \cdot) , there exists a Smarandache f, g principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) such that $(H, *) \simeq (G, \circ)$. So, $(G, \cdot) \simeq (G, \circ)$.

Conversely, let $(G, \cdot) \simeq (G, \circ)$, using the fact in Corollary 4.3 again, for any arbitrary S-isotope $(H, *)$ of (G, \cdot) , there exists a Smarandache f, g principal isotope (G, \circ) of (G, \cdot) such that $(G, \circ) \simeq (H, *)$. Therefore, $(G, \cdot) \simeq (H, *)$.

Corollary 5.3. A S-loop is a GS-loop if and only if it is S-isomorphic to all its Smarandache f, g principal isotopes.

Proof. This follows by the definition of a GS-loop and Corollary 5.2.

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